

What is DiBL?

DiBL is a model to support structured, facilitated group deliberation using narratives, dilemmas, and participatory prompts.

Each DiBL case study combines an online interface with in-person facilitation to help communities explore climate-related challenges, ranging from job transitions and water scarcity to sustainable housing and future prosperity.

DIBL CASE STUDIES - GREAT PROJECT

Purpose of this document:

This short guide compiles all publicly available DiBL (Dilemma Based Learning) case study materials created within the GREAT project. These tools were originally published across multiple blog posts and platform pages, but are gathered here to ensure long-term, citable access, especially for educators, policymakers, researchers, and community facilitators.

How are these resources organised?

Each section includes:

- A short description of the case study
- Link to the blog
- Link to the DiBL view page
- Links to the downloadable facilitation guides

Case studies included:

- GCS2 Waterwise
- GCS3 Green Jobs
- GCS4 Green Roofs
- GCS7 Prosper

GCS2 WATERWISE

Summary:

Waterwise focuses on water scarcity, behavioural change, and community-level decisions about resilience during drought conditions.

Links:

Blog overview:

<https://www.greatproject.gg/blog/toolkit-waterwise>

DiBL playable case:

<https://web.dibl.eu/caseview/7717/b7845201-e1e6-4ef2-b9c9-08afa3191667/facilitator>

Facilitation guide:

<https://dibl.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/WATERWISE-Facilitation-guide.pdf>

GCS3 GREEN JOBS

Summary:

The Green Jobs DiBL explores workforce transitions, emerging green sectors, and the dilemmas faced by communities as they adapt to climate-driven economic change.

Links:

Blog overview:

<https://www.greatproject.gg/blog/toolkit-waterwise>

DiBL playable case:

<https://web.dibl.eu/caseview/7450/42a4a640-13c2-46b7-b386-82b8ada0e02a/facilitator>

Facilitation guide EN:

<https://dibl.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/GREEN-JOBS-Facilitation-guide.pdf>

Facilitation guide DE:

<https://dibl.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/GREEN-JOBS-Facilitation-guide-GERMAN.pdf>

GCS4 GREEN ROOFTOPS

Summary:

Green Rooftops looks at climate-resilient architecture and the trade-offs of integrating nature-based solutions into urban development.

Links:

Blog overview:

<https://www.greatproject.gg/blog/toolkit-green-rooftops>

DiBL playable case part 1:

<https://web.dibl.eu/caseview/7547/04a1a543-2719-499b-9829-2b182fcd9498/facilitator>

DiBL playable case part 2:

<https://web.dibl.eu/caseview/7468/de68f577-680e-4627-9320-70818bd42920/facilitator>

Facilitation guide: coming soon

GCS7 PROSPER

Summary:

Prosper explores local wellbeing, collective visions for the future, and how communities balance economic, social, and climate priorities.

Links:

Blog overview:

<https://www.greatproject.gg/blog/toolkit-waterwise>

DiBL playable case:

<https://web.dibl.eu/caseview/7849/fc580d64-d5fe-4cc9-8fb1-d49dc1558c4e/facilitator>

Facilitation guide:

https://dibl.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/Prosper_-DiBL-edition-facilitator-guide.pdf